

ESKAPE PATHOGENS: THE PERPETUAM MOBILE OF ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE IN HOSPITALS IN THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA
Patogenii SKAPA: mobilitatea perpetuă a rezistenței antimicrobiene în spitalele din Republica Moldova

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Lucia GALBEN

<https://orcid.org/0009-0005-3154-7193>

PhD student, microbiologist specialist, Republican Clinical Hospital “Timofei Moșneaga” USMF “Nicolae Testemițanu”

E-mail: luciagalben@mail.ru

Oana-Simina IACONI

<https://orcid.org/0009-0003-3139-7004>

assistant professor, PhD student, Microbiology and Immunology Discipline, “Nicolae Testemițanu” University of Medical Sciences

E-mail: oanasimina.iaconi@usmf.md

Greta BALAN

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3704-3584>

Associate Professor, PhD in Medical Sciences, Department of Microbiology and Immunology, “Nicolae Testemițanu” USMF

E-mail: greta.balan@usmf.md

Alina FERDOHLEB

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1344-5466>

Associate Professor, PhD in Medical Sciences, project director, Department of Social Medicine and Management “Nicolae Testemițanu”, USMF “Nicolae Testemițanu”

E-mail: alina.ferdohleb@usmf.md

Rezumat. Rezistența antimicrobiană (RAM) este un inamic tăcut care ucide milioane de pacienți la nivel mondial. Acest fenomen este un mecanism adaptiv împotriva schimbărilor dăunătoare din mediu, conceput pentru a proteja microorganismele. Se găsește în bacterii și ciuperci și se manifestă prin ineficiența tratamentului pentru pacienții care suferă de boli infecțioase. Potrivit Organizației Mondiale a Sănătății, aceasta reprezintă o amenințare tot mai mare pentru sănătatea publică și în special pentru țările cu venituri mici și medii, deoarece povara economică a tratamentului pe termen lung și indisponibilitatea medicamentelor eficiente sau a altor tratamente alternative reduc șansele de rezultate pozitive pentru bolile infecțioase determinate de RAM. Rapoartele recente arată că agenții patogeni ESKAPE sunt responsabili pentru majoritatea deceselor asociate și atribuite RAM. Această cercetare și-a propus să prezinte date actuale privind situația privind rezistența antimicrobiană într-un spital model din Republica Moldova, în speranța că datele obținute vor încuraja autoritățile și părțile interesate să caute soluții optime pentru atenuarea acestui fenomen.

Cuvinte cheie: rezistență antimicrobiană, bacterii rezistente la medicamente multiple, agenți patogeni ESKAPE, sănătate publică, țări cu venituri mici și medii.

Introduction. Antimicrobial resistance was first mentioned publicly in 1945 by Alexander Fleming, who received the Nobel Prize in Physiology or Medicine for his discovery of penicillin. Half a century later, European and global public health surveillance organizations determined that excessive consumption of antimicrobials causes the development of bacterial resistance mechanisms as an adaptive response to environmental changes¹. Healthcare practices involving the administration of antimicrobials for prophylactic purposes before and after surgery, multiple cases of co-infection and superinfection in medical institutions, and self-administration of antimicrobials among the population have led to an increase in cases of infections with multi- and pan-resistant pathogens². In order to mitigate the impact of AMR on public health and the economy through the implementation of appropriate solutions, many countries around the world have mapped the situation regarding antimicrobial consumption, the population's knowledge and practices regarding AMR, and the resistance profile of pathogens that form the microbiome of healthcare facilities³. Studies have shown that low- and middle-income countries (Tanzania, Vietnam) face increased levels of epidemiological indicators of AMR, with an increased number of antimicrobial-resistant species and strains, and that the population's knowledge and practices regarding antimicrobial consumption have not been fully assessed, compared to developed countries⁴.

The Republic of Moldova, being an LMIC in Eastern Europe, faces the same problems. However, considerable efforts have been made in recent years to improve the situation. Thus, in the last three years alone, active measures have been taken to address the impact of AMR on the healthcare system, public health and the national economy through the publication of guidelines, methodological recommendations and informational and educational materials for various population groups. Mapping antibiotic consumption at national level between

¹ Lobanovska, M.; Pilla, G. Penicillin's Discovery and Antibiotic Resistance: Lessons for the Future?, in: *The Yale Journal of Biology and Medicine*, 2017, vol. 90, nr. 1, pp. 135–145; Verbeke, G.; Huys, I.; Pirnay, J. P.; Jennes, S.; Chanishvili, N.; Scheres, J.; Górski, A.; De Vos, D.; Ceulemans, C. Taking bacteriophage therapy seriously: a moral argument, in: *Biomed Res Int*, 2014, 2014, art. 621316. DOI: 10.1155/2014/621316.

² GBD 2021 Antimicrobial Resistance Collaborators. Global burden of bacterial antimicrobial resistance 1990–2021: a systematic analysis with forecasts to 2050. *Lancet* (London, England), 2024, vol. 404, nr. 10459, pp. 1199–1226. DOI: 10.1016/S0140-6736(24)01867-1; Collignon, P.; Beggs, J. J.; Walsh, T. R.; Gandra, S.; Laxminarayan, R. Anthropological and socioeconomic factors contributing to global antimicrobial resistance: a univariate and multivariable analysis, in: *The Lancet Planetary Health*, 2018, vol. 2, nr. 9, p. e398–e405; Țapu, L.; Ferdohleb, A.; Spinei, L.; Borrego, C. Knowledge, Attitudes and Practices Regarding Antimicrobial Resistance in Low- and Middle-Income Countries: Narrative Synthesis, in: *One Health and Risk Management*, ediție specială, 2024, supl. 1, p. 47–53.

³ Gualano, M. R.; Gili, R.; Scaioli, G.; et al. General population's knowledge and attitudes about antibiotics: A systematic review and meta-analysis, in: *Pharmacoepidemiol Drug Saf*, 2015, vol. 24, pp. 2–10.

⁴ Sulis, G.; Sayood, S.; Gandra, S. Antimicrobial resistance in low- and middle-income countries: current status and future directions, in: *Expert Rev Anti Infect Ther*, 2022, vol. 20, nr. 2, pp. 147–160. DOI: 10.1080/14787210.2021.1951705; Camara, N.; Moremi, N.; Mghamba, J.; Eliakimu, E.; Shumba, E.; Ondo, P.; Egyir, B. Surveillance of antimicrobial resistance in human health in Tanzania: 2016–2021, in: *Afr J Lab Med*, 2023, vol. 12, nr. 1, art. 2053. DOI: 10.4102/ajlm.v12i1.2053; Van An, N.; Hoang, L. H.; Le, H. H. L.; Thai Son, N.; Hong, L. T.; Viet, T. T.; et al. Distribution and Antibiotic Resistance Characteristics of Bacteria Isolated from Blood Culture in a Teaching Hospital in Vietnam During 2014–2021, in: *Infect Drug Resist*, 2023, vol. 16, p. 1677–1692. DOI: 10.2147/IDR.S402278.

2018 and 2021 showed increased consumption of antimicrobials in the North RDD, Central RDD and the **Gagauz ATU** regions. The highest number of defined daily doses consumed was recorded in the Fălești district and Chișinău municipality. In this context, a series of tools for popularising knowledge in the form of storybooks and calendars were developed⁵.

With regard to causative agents, the World Health Organization has determined that, globally, pathogens in the ESKAPE group are the main carriers of resistance genotypes and phenotypes to various groups of antimicrobials, particularly β -lactams⁶. Extended-spectrum beta-lactamases (ESBLs) are enzymes that inactivate most penicillins and cephalosporins, including those of generations III and IV, as well as monobactams (e.g., aztreonam), but do not affect cephamycins or carbapenems, and are common among *Enterobacteriaceae*. Thus, *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *K. pneumoniae*, *A. baumannii*, *P. aeruginosa* and *Enterobacter spp* have become the main diagnostic targets of the public health surveillance systems⁷.

This study aims to determine the resistance profile of pathogens isolated from various human biosubstrates from patients admitted to a model hospital who do not respond to the administered antimicrobial treatment.

Materials and Methods

For this study, 101 patients were selected from whom urine, blood, pharyngeal/wound exudate or faecal samples were collected, depending on the nosocomial form with which they were admitted to the Timofei Mosneaga Republican Clinical Hospital between 2024 and 2025.

Bacterial strains (species) were identified using classical culture-based methods and automated methods – Vitek2Compact (Bio Mérieux, France), following the internal protocol of the Microbiology Laboratory of the hospital. The susceptibility of the strains was tested using disk-diffusion method and Vitek2Compact (AST cards).

During the screening stage, all clinical isolates suspected based on their resistance profile were tested for ESBL. Strains that showed resistance to third-generation cephalosporins (ceftazidime, cefotaxime, ceftriaxone, cefexime) and fourth-generation cephalosporins (cefepime). To detect carbapenemase producers (CPE), screening was performed on enterobacterial strains resistant to carbapenems (meropenem, imipenem, ertapenem, doripenem). For the phenotypic confirmation of the production of β -lactamase and carbapenemase enzymes, the double-disc synergy test was used. Extended-spectrum β -lactamases (ESBL) were detected using discs impregnated with ceftriaxone (CRO 30), amoxicillin 20/clavulanic acid 10 (AUG 30), and ceftazidime (CAZ 30).

The proportion of strains relative to the total number of isolates, the frequency of multi-drug-resistant bacterial strains within the studied species, and the share of strains exhibiting phenotypically expressed resistance mechanisms were assessed.

⁵ Ferdohleb, A.; Ciobanu, E.; Croitoru, C.; Bălan, G.; Paraschiv, A. *Convergența provocărilor globale în țările cu venituri mici și medii*. Monografie. Chișinău: Print-Caro, 2025, 232 p.; Bălan, G.; Ferdohleb, A.; Iaconi, O.-S.; Ciobanu, E.; Lozneanu, I.; Croitoru, C. *O istorie despre rezistența la antimicrobiene*. Chișinău, 2024, 12 p.

⁶ World Health Organization (WHO). Global Priority List of Antibiotic Resistant Bacteria to Guide Research, Discovery, and Development of New Antibiotics. Geneva, 2017. (Document online).

⁷ Iunac, D.; Galben, L.; Ferdohleb, A.; Bălan, G. Mecanisme de rezistență la antimicrobiene a tulpinilor de *Staphylococcus aureus*: sinteză narativă, in: *Общественное здоровье, экономика и менеджмент в медицине*, 2023, nr. 2(95), pp. 38–43. DOI: 10.52556/2587-3873.2023.2(95).05; Iaconi, O.-S.; Ferdohleb, A.; Bălan, G.; Galben, L.; Dziewit, L.; Borrego, C. M. The public health problem and resistant bacteria in low and middle-income countries, in: *One Health & Risk Management*, 2024, vol. 5, nr. 1, pp. 34–42.

Results

A total of 101 patients were enrolled in the study and biological samples were collected from them. Of these, 55.9% were men and 44.1% were women, all of whom were adults. The distribution of isolated strains according to the ward showed that most multidrug-resistant strains were isolated from patients admitted to the Intensive Care Unit for septic surgery (16.0%), Urology (12.1%), Nephrology (9.5%), General Surgery (7.4%), and Septic Surgery (6.5%) (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Proportion of strains with multiple resistance by wards

Of the total of seven species that make up the ESKAPE group, five representatives were identified: *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *K. pneumoniae*, *A. baumannii*, and *P. aeruginosa*. The distribution of isolated species according to biosubstrates shows that most multi-resistant strains of *K. pneumoniae* and *E. coli* were isolated from urine (Fig. 2 a and b), accounting for 40.7% and 69.4% of the total number, respectively. Most multi-resistant strains of *K. pneumoniae* were isolated from urine, pharyngeal exudate (37%) and wound exudate (9.9%). For *E. coli* strains, the proportions are 16.1% for wound exudate and 6.4% for pharyngeal exudate.

Multidrug-resistant *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* strains were predominantly isolated from pharyngeal exudate (45.7%), wound exudate (30.5%) and urine (20.3%). Half of the identified *Acinetobacter baumannii* strains were isolated from pharyngeal exudate and more than 1/5 from blood. *S. aureus* strains were isolated from three biosubstrates: wound exudate (45.4%), pharyngeal exudate (36.4%) and blood (18.2%) (fig. 3).

The results obtained are consistent with other studies conducted in the Republic of Moldova and in the region⁸.

⁸ Ciobanu, E., Croitoru, C., Balan, G., Bernic, V., Burduniuc, O., & Ferdohleb, A. (2022, aprilie). Phage treatment and wetland technology as intervention strategy to prevent dissemination of antibiotic resistance in surface waters: A project launch in low-middle income countries of Eastern Europe, in: *Materialele Conferinței Științifice Naționale cu participare internațională „Water and health: achievements and challenges”*. *One Health and Risk Management*, 3(2S), p. 28; Iaconi, O.-S.; Ferdohleb, A.; Bălan, G.; Galben, L.; Dziewit, L.; Borrego, C. M. The public health problem and resistant bacteria in low and middle-income countries, in: *One Health & Risk Management*, 2024, vol. 5, nr. 1, p. 34–42; Petca, R. C.; Mareș, C.; Petca, A.; Negoită, S.; Popescu, R. I.; Boț, M.; et al. Spectrum and Antibiotic Resistance of Uropathogens in Romanian Females, in: *Antibiotics* (Basel),

Figure 2. Distribution of K.pneumoniae and E.coli isolated according to biological substrat

Figure 3. Distribution of isolated multi-drug A. baumannii, P.aeruginosa and S.aureus by biological sample

Conclusion

Antimicrobial resistance is a major global public health issue requiring interventions at the levels of surveillance, diagnosis, treatment and society. It was found that ESKAPE pathogens are the major AMR reservoirs in the model hospital. Due to this study, an increased proportion of multidrug-resistant bacterial strains was identified. These figures are worrying, but they serve as an argument for implementing measures to mitigate the phenomenon at national level.

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2020, vol. 9, nr. 8, art. 472. DOI: 10.3390/antibiotics9080472; Manolitsis, I.; Feretzakis, G.; Katsimberis, S.; Angelopoulos, P.; Loupelis, E.; Skarmoutsou, N.; et al. A 2-Year Audit on Antibiotic Resistance Patterns from a Urology Department in Greece, in: *Journal of Clinical Medicine*, 2023, vol. 12, nr. 9, art. 3180. DOI: 10.3390/jcm12093180